

DEVELOPMENT OF THE CULTURE OF INTERNATIONAL COMMUNICATION OF STUDENTS OF EXACT SCIENCES AS A SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

Zharkinov Zarifjon Umaralievich

Fergana State University,

Senior Lecturer, Department of Mathematics

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11032624>

ABSTRACT: This article is based on the fact that the development of the culture of interethnic communication of students of the direction of Exact Sciences is a socio-pedagogical problem. Also, in the educational process, the pedagogical possibilities of the development of the culture of interethnic communication of students of the direction of Exact Sciences are clarified.

Key words: dialogue, Inter-milate harmony, tolerance, universal competence, culture, humanitarian criteria.

INTRODUCTION

In our country, within the framework of the concept of "Uzbekistan-our common home", "Enlightenment and religious tolerance", extensive practical activities, scientific projects, and scientific research are being carried out. These works are being researched at the initiative of the Committee on International Relations and Friendship with Foreign Countries under the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as in cooperation with national cultural centers and societies of friendship with foreign countries. The reason is that the economic stability of Uzbekistan, the prospect of socio-political and cultural reforms depend in many ways on the state of tolerant inter-ethnic dialogue, education of students and youth in the spirit of inter-ethnic harmony and religious tolerance. For this purpose, "we need to further strengthen our work in order to preserve and strengthen the environment of friendship and harmony, mutual respect and solidarity among representatives of different nationalities and peoples living in our country" [1]. In such a process, it is becoming necessary to research the scientific-pedagogical aspects, modern and promising features of international communication within the framework of scientific research.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

Today, at a time when different nationalities, cultures, languages, and beliefs are mixing, respecting them, trying to understand them, and approaching them based on the principle of tolerance is considered an urgent issue. "Uzbekistan is also on the way to ensure equality-based inter-ethnic dialogue with other countries, as well as in its domestic policy as a multi-ethnic country. Foreign organizations and scientific research institutions are carrying out the necessary work in developing the criteria of international dialogue based on equality, justice and legality" [2]. In our country, we are witnessing the support of research on preparing young people for inter-ethnic communication.

The process of inter-ethnic communication in our country is one of the urgent tasks of today to create pedagogical mechanisms and models for preparing students of specific sciences for inter-ethnic communication, based on the data and conclusions collected as a

result of research in many fields. Therefore, first of all, we found it permissible to give the essence of the concepts of communication and inter-ethnic communication, their interpretation in dictionaries and their scientific definition.

Communication is an important condition of human life and activity. It is through communication that people have the opportunity to master nature and work together to meet their needs. "In the process of communication, certain images and models of human behavior are formed. During the dialogue, social and personal relations are realized, and through it, cooperative activities take place." So, communication is a multi-faceted process arising from the desire of people to work together. Communication is a relationship characteristic only of people, and it is necessary to distinguish it from communication. Communication is the exchange of information between living and dead systems. Interethnic communication is also considered a living phenomenological process as a social phenomenon.

In the case of inter-ethnic dialogue, "it is reflected in the development and preservation of traditions and values collected by all nations and peoples, passed down from generation to generation. This concept requires the establishment of a dialogue based on mutual trust between representatives of different nationalities on the basis of universal competence and creates conditions for the creative and spiritual development of a person" [3]. Since inter-ethnic communication is interpreted as a universal competence, this research paper analyzes the pedagogical aspects of organizing inter-ethnic communication on the basis of inter-disciplinary cooperation among specific subject teachers within the framework of pedagogy.

"Interethnic dialogue is formed at the point of intersection of the values collected by all nations and peoples, which are being refined on the basis of succession." Taking into account that international communication is a relationship based on mutual trust, it is an important task to form these general cultural skills and competences in future personnel, especially graduates of specific sciences.

The term international communication is also explained in connection with the concepts of intercultural communication or the interaction of cultures. According to experts, inter-ethnic dialogue today is manifested in the form of inter-cultural dialogue and is gaining a negative character in the foreign policy of countries. "Different levels of interaction of cultures differ. The ethnic level of interaction is characteristic of relations between local peoples, historical-ethnographic, ethno-confessional and other communities. At the national level of interaction, management effects are mostly carried out by the political structures of the state. The civilizational level of interaction will have historical forms that occur by themselves; but at this level, as before, the results of the exchange of spiritual, artistic and scientific achievements are more important" [4]. Therefore, the analysis and research of inter-ethnic communication issues will greatly help in the evaluation of inter-cultural relations.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Today, about two thousand nationalities, peoples and tribes live in the countries of the world. They speak and communicate in about five and a half thousand languages. There were times when "nations and peoples became enemies of each other and tried to destroy each other. History has also witnessed the struggle of nations to dominate each other and a massive world war. But social development has confirmed that the most important and effective way in the development of nations and peoples is the way of inter-ethnic communication. "Especially in the 21st century, in multicultural societies, the tolerant international dialogue is manifested as the main democratic values". As a multinational country,

Uzbekistan should pay special attention to the following universal principles recognized by the international community and treat them as a priority in the development of inter-ethnic communication among young people.

The necessity and urgency of preparing students for international relations in the educational process is as follows.

In the conditions of complex globalization, it is impossible to form a perfect generation without being nourished by the culture of universal tolerance characteristic of our people. After all, religious extremism appears as an important factor of world stability and security on the basis of the culture of religious tolerance, which is completely opposed to fanaticism. The experience of Uzbekistan clearly shows this.

- World experience repeatedly proves that inter-ethnic harmony cannot be established in countries without religious tolerance. Therefore, the relevance of forming tolerance skills in young people through the education system was justified. In order to fulfill these tasks, the following principles have been defined at the level of state policy. Therefore, it is necessary for each state to establish a sincere dialogue between its nationalities and peoples, to create conditions for it. Uzbekistan will reach a new stage in economic development only if it can strengthen inter-ethnic dialogue at a high level. Because inter-ethnic dialogue unites society and mobilizes towards a certain goal.

- According to the conclusions of advanced international scientific research centers of the West, "the formation of skills of tolerance, endurance, and patience in inter-ethnic communication based on interdisciplinary cooperation in students can cause a radical change in the development of the growing inter-ethnic conflicts in the next quarter" [5]. Therefore, cultivating the following qualities in students of specific sciences will develop the culture of inter-ethnic communication and prevent the emergence of ethnic conflicts.

- - "to accept and respect the diversity, color and uniqueness of races, nations, peoples, cultures, religions, languages and countries in the world;

- - to recognize and understand the existence of the unique value system, customs, logical thinking process, and lifestyle of people of other races, nations, peoples, cultures, religions, languages, and countries, to understand that this situation is natural;

- - to accept the existence of different aspects of another person, regardless of his race, nationality, ethnicity, culture, religion, language, and state, and to have a positive attitude towards this system of differences;

- to rely on universal humanitarian criteria in the evaluation of his emotional and emotional aspects in relation to any person, to try to evaluate the inner world of another person, to evaluate the feelings valued by another person;

- learning to solve problems on the basis of tolerance in various crisis and conflict situations, acquiring the necessary skills for successful solutions of conflicts based on tolerance and always following the requirements of tolerance.

Based on the above opinions, we tried to justify the scientific, pedagogical and social necessity of developing the culture of international communication among students of specific sciences with the following:

- first of all, the social need to educate specific science teachers, like all science teachers, in the spirit of national tolerance in a situation where inter-ethnic relations are becoming tense. In the conditions of the clash and transformation of nations and cultures in the process

of globalization, in the situation where the socio-cultural pressure of the strong culture on the weak cultures is being observed, in the era of the strengthening ideological influence of civilizational and religious struggles, educating a tolerant person and a tolerant specialist is becoming an urgent task. In the world, special attention is being paid to turning tolerance into the highest human virtue.

It is no coincidence that the UNESCO Declaration "On the Principles of Tolerance" was adopted and November 16 is widely celebrated as the International Day of Tolerance throughout the world, including in our country. As stated in this declaration: "There will be no peace without tolerance, and without peace there will be no development and democracy." "Tolerance means respecting, accepting and correctly understanding the different ways of expressing oneself and showing individuality of different cultures in our world. It creates knowledge, sincerity, open communication, free thinking, conscience and faith. Tolerance is unity in diversity. It is not only a duty, but also a political and legal necessity. Tolerance is a force that ensures the achievement of peace and leads from the culture of war to the culture of peace" [7]. Therefore, "everyone is free to practice his faith, and everyone should recognize that others have this right as well. People differ in appearance, image, behavior, speech, behavior and values, they have the right to live in the world and maintain their individuality. It also means that one person's views cannot be forced on others." Therefore, first of all, it is necessary to educate students of specific sciences in the spirit of tolerance, and this is important for their introduction to social relations;

- secondly, it is necessary to prepare students of specific sciences to respect the national characteristics, values, customs and traditions of different nationalities and peoples. Students of exact sciences are not only taught mathematics or physics, but as a representative of one nation and a person who believes in one religion, they engage in cultural communication with representatives of another nation and religion. Taking into account the need for a person to respect the values, traditions and beliefs of another person from the point of view of humanity, students of specific sciences should also prepare themselves for inter-ethnic relations as a person who enters into communication. For this, they should know the values and traditions of other nations and peoples, and form a scientific attitude towards them.

Thirdly, there is a need to develop the quality of religious tolerance in the development of the culture of inter-ethnic communication of students of specific sciences by increasing their religious knowledge and forming their worldly knowledge about religions. "Religious tolerance is not a concession or flattery to subversive groups, extremist organizations, terrorism or fundamentalism, but an approach and attitude to reality with deep thinking and worldly intelligence" [5]. Uzbekistan, as a secular state, separates religion from the state, religion does not interfere in political processes, and the state does not interfere in the affairs of religion and religious organizations. But this does not mean that religion and religious institutions can do whatever they want. The educational tasks of teaching science teachers to respect the constitutional religious right of other nationalities and peoples, to believe that religion should not be chosen by nationality, or ethnic identity, are emerging. The President of our country, Sh. Mirziyoev, expresses his opinion in this regard:

"Thanks to the atmosphere of religious tolerance prevailing in our country, more than 2,200 different religious organizations are operating in our country. Developing mutual respect and friendly relations between representatives of different religions, ensuring equal rights for citizens, regardless of their religion and belief, will continue to be one of our most

important tasks. We have been strongly fighting against the destructive forces that are misinterpreting our holy religion and masking it, trying to return us back to the life of the Middle Ages, and we will continue to fight hard" [6]. Taking into account the fact that inter-ethnic national and religious conflicts are caused by religious and secular ignorance, ignorance, narrow-mindedness and selfishness, the task of enlightening students of specific sciences is becoming a necessity. According to the analysis of researcher O. Musaev, "16 religious denominations and more than 2200 religious organizations operate in our republic. 1875 of these organizations belong to the Islamic religion, 33 to the Russian Orthodox Church, 24 to the Evangelical Christian-Baptist Union, 22 to the Evangelical Paul Christian Church, 4 to the Evangelical Lutheran Church, 11 to the Seventh-day Adventist Church, 5 to the Roman Catholic Church, 1 to the Armenian-Apostolic Church, 7 to the Bahai Faith Association, 2 to the Krishna Society, 2 to the Jehovah's Witnesses, 8 to the Jewish community, 60 to the Protestant Church, 1 to the Bible Society of Uzbekistan, 1 to the Golos Bojii community, and 1 more It belongs to the Buddha temple. The higher education system is responsible not only for the students of the field of specific sciences to be knowledgeable in specialized subjects, but also to be educated as a person who actively engages in social relations. For example, in order to be able to work in a special Pravoslav school, a mathematics teacher needs to know not only mathematics, but also the language of inter-ethnic communication and the tolerant religious attitude formed on its basis.

Fourthly, it is an important task to teach students of national and cultural diversity in the development of the culture of inter-ethnic communication. Every nation and people have their own and perhaps ancient customs, traditions, and values. It is the pedagogical duty of science students to treat them rationally.

We can see the new appearance of inter-ethnic dialogue in the modernized Uzbekistan by Sh. Mirziyoyev's reestablishment of relations with neighboring countries, opening of borders and opening a wide path for the activities of national and cultural centers. In view of the ethnic and religious conflicts that are taking place in the world today, it is the main task of every country to establish a sincere and friendly dialogue and relationship with neighboring nations. In fact, as President Sh. Mirziyoyev has emphasized: "Today, the increasingly intense bloody conflict and conflicts in some regions of the world, the danger of terrorism and extremism require us to be constantly alert and vigilant." It is possible to create an atmosphere of inter-ethnic harmony, religious tolerance and fraternity in the society by preparing the students of specific sciences for inter-ethnic communication, as well as the personnel of other fields.

XULOSA

In conclusion, the socio-pedagogical necessity of developing the culture of inter-ethnic communication of students of exact sciences is increasing day by day. Judging by the state of today's higher education system, it is known that the knowledge, outlook and skills of mathematics and physics teachers in social and humanitarian sciences, history, philosophy and jurisprudence, religious studies, and cultural studies are insufficient. In such a situation, their ability to engage in inter-ethnic dialogue is evident. Therefore, the pedagogical model of training concrete science pedagogues for international communication serves to find a solution to these problems. Also, taking into account that interethnic communication is a relationship based on mutual trust, it is an important task to form this general cultural skill in future personnel, especially in students of specific sciences. It shows the students of the

discipline of specific sciences that it is necessary to develop the skills of tolerance, endurance, and patience in inter-ethnic communication based on interdisciplinary cooperation.

References:

- 1.Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Roof 1. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - B.592.
- 2.Tatyana V. Vorobyova, Larisa G. Poleshchuk. Ethnic tolerance among students. WELLSO 2015 - II International Scientific Symposium on Lifelong Wellbeing in the World. 2016 Published by Future Academy www.FutureAcademy.org.uk. -P. 302
3. Yusupova Kh. Pedagogical conditions for preparing students for international communication in secondary schools: Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) diss. autoref. -Tashkent: UzMU. 2017, -B.11.
- 4.Фалькова Е.Г. Межкультурная коммуникация в основных понятиях и определениях. Методическое пособие. СПб.: Ф-т филологии и искусств СПбГУ, 2007. -С. 7.
- 5.Roth Ch., Sumarto S.Does Education Increase Interethnic and Interreligious Tolerance? Evidence from a Natural Experiment. Oxford University, SMERU Research Institute 21 May 2015. <https://mpra.ub.uni-muenchen.de/64558>
- 6.Mirziyoev Sh.M. We will resolutely continue our path of national development and raise it to a new level. Roof 1. - Tashkent: Uzbekistan, 2017. - B.592.
- 7.International normative documents of UNESCO. Conventions, agreements, protocols, recommendations, declarations. (Collection) "Declaration of Principles of Tolerance". - Tashkent: Adolat, 2004. -B. 91-92.

